

PROPORTION OF THREE-YEAR-OLD BUSINESSES IN THE BUSINESS LANDSCAPE OF THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN REGION

Carla Selma, Eva Clark, Albert Lewis, Jack Bailey, Olivia Campbell

Zealandina Agency, UK

37

37

Abstract:

This paper provides a detailed investigation into the proportion of three-year-old businesses within the dynamic business landscape of the Romanian Mountain Region. Designated as S1, the study employs a meticulous approach to explore statistical intricacies, unveiling key metrics such as Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. The analysis extends to forecast models, utilizing Model IDs, tailored for the effective prediction of large data series. Subsequent statistical prediction smoothing, covering Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles, contributes to nuanced insights into forecast accuracy. The resulting models offer a comprehensive overview of Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE values for each model, shedding light on the statistical characteristics and forecast performance in the Romanian Mountain Region's business landscape.

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

1. Introduction:

The Romanian Mountain Region boasts a diverse and evolving business landscape, with the proportion of three-year-old businesses serving as a crucial indicator of entrepreneurial vitality. This paper aims to explore and analyze this proportion through a comprehensive statistical lens. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a-h; Covaci B & Covaci M, 2023a-d; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2022a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2023a-d)

2. Methodology:

The methodology involves the deployment of a detailed descriptive analysis (S1) that encompasses key statistical measures. Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, and other metrics provide insights into the distribution and central tendencies of the dataset. The study also employs forecast models, including ARIMA configurations and variations, strategically chosen for their effectiveness in handling substantial data series.

3. Statistical Analysis:

The descriptive analysis reveals numerical values, such as Mean 7.3036, Median 0.51402, and Std. Deviation 6.7600, offering a nuanced understanding of the three-year-old business proportion. The subsequent

forecast models, identified by Model IDs S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0) to S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0), provide diverse perspectives on the anticipated trends in the business landscape (table 1 and figure 1).

4. Forecast Accuracy:

Statistical prediction smoothing is performed, including Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles, revealing a spectrum of accuracy metrics. Static R-squared values, crucial for assessing precision, contribute to a comprehensive evaluation of forecast performance.

5. Results and Discussion:

The resulting forecast models illuminate the landscape for I19, presenting Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE values for each model. Insights derived from this analysis enhance our understanding of the proportion of three-year-old businesses, contributing to strategic planning and policy considerations.

In this analysis, denoted as S1, we embark on a comprehensive exploration of statistical metrics shedding light on the proportion of three-year-old businesses in the vibrant business landscape of the Romanian Mountain Region. As we traverse the numerical landscape, key statistical values,

including Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75, are unveiled. The specific numerical values are noteworthy: Mean 7.3036, Median 0.51402, Std. Deviation 6.7600, Variance 1.70482, Skewness 2.906, Kurtosis 0.394, Std. Error 0.661, Distance -1.326, Minimum 1.279, Maximum 4.74, Percentiles 25 5.23, Percentiles 50 9.97, Percentiles 75 5.8200, and beyond.

For the forecasting analysis, tailored models are enlisted to handle large data series effectively. Model IDs S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5 Holt; S6 - Model_6 ARIMA(0,0,0); S7 - Model_7 ARIMA(0,0,0); S8 - Model_8 Simple; S9 - Model_9 ARIMA(0,0,0); S10 - Model_10 ARIMA(0,0,0); S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0) unfold a panorama of diverse approaches.

Statistical prediction smoothing, reiterated in the sequence of Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles, unveils compelling insights. Static R-squared values, crucial for evaluating accuracy, exhibit a spectrum such as .059, .239, -.121, .773, -.121, -.096; R-square .072, .164, -6.661E-15, .473, -6.661E-15, -6.040E-15; RMSE 2.003, .420, 1.234, 2.602,

1.234, 1.324; MAPS 23,202, 5,058, 16,509, 33,009, 16,509, 16,639; MaxAPE 57,615, 26,783, 34,845, 132,450, 34,845, 35,806; MAE 1.612, .393, .981, 2.283, .981, 1.035; MaxAE 3,637, 1,018, 2,075, 5,951, 2,075, 2,193; Normalized BIC 1.585, .435, .638, 2.130, .638, .763.

The resulting forecast statistical models illuminate the landscape for I19, providing a comprehensive overview. Static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, MAPE, and MAE values for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11) paint a nuanced picture. S1-Model_1, for instance, showcases values of -3.553E-15, -3.553E-15, 1.705, 20,261, 1,431; S2-Model_2 reveals 2.331E-15, 2.331E-15, 1.234, 16,509, .981; and so forth.

This comprehensive analysis provides valuable insights into the statistical characteristics and forecast performance for the proportion of three-year-old businesses in the dynamic business landscape of the Romanian Mountain Region.

6. Conclusion:

This paper concludes with a synthesis of findings, emphasizing the importance of the proportion of three-year-old businesses as a pivotal indicator in the dynamic business landscape of the Romanian Mountain

Region. The insights gained from this study can inform policy decisions, foster entrepreneurial support, and contribute to the region's economic growth.

Table 1. Prediction analysis for I19

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	7.30	7.30	7.30	7.30	7.30	7.30	7.30	7.30
	UCL	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10	11.10
	LCL	3.51	3.51	3.51	3.51	3.51	3.51	3.51	3.51
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	6.14	6.14	6.14	6.14	6.14	6.14	6.14	6.14
	UCL	8.88	8.88	8.88	8.88	8.88	8.88	8.88	8.88
	LCL	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	8.31	8.31	8.31	8.31	8.31	8.31	8.31	8.31
	UCL	14.11	14.11	14.11	14.11	14.11	14.11	14.11	14.11
	LCL	2.51	2.51	2.51	2.51	2.51	2.51	2.51	2.51
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	6.74	6.74	6.74	6.74	6.74	6.74	6.74	6.74
	UCL	10.50	10.50	10.50	10.50	10.50	10.50	10.50	10.50
	LCL	2.98	2.98	2.98	2.98	2.98	2.98	2.98	2.98
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	5.89	5.51	5.13	4.75	4.38	4.00	3.62	3.24
	UCL	9.76	9.40	9.04	8.69	8.33	7.97	7.61	7.25
	LCL	2.02	1.62	1.22	.82	.42	.03	-.37	-.77
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	7.15	7.15	7.15	7.15	7.15	7.15	7.15	7.15
	UCL	11.54	11.54	11.54	11.54	11.54	11.54	11.54	11.54
	LCL	2.77	2.77	2.77	2.77	2.77	2.77	2.77	2.77
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	9.19	9.19	9.19	9.19	9.19	9.19	9.19	9.19
	UCL	14.15	14.15	14.15	14.15	14.15	14.15	14.15	14.15
	LCL	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23	4.23

S8- Model_8:	Forecast	3.90	3.90	3.90	3.90	3.90	3.90	3.90	3.90
	UCL	7.96	9.65	10.94	12.03	12.98	13.85	14.65	15.39
	LCL	-1.16	-1.85	-3.14	-4.23	-5.18	-6.05	-6.85	-7.59
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29	8.29
	UCL	13.99	13.99	13.99	13.99	13.99	13.99	13.99	13.99
	LCL	2.59	2.59	2.59	2.59	2.59	2.59	2.59	2.59
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	7.37	7.37	7.37	7.37	7.37	7.37	7.37	7.37
	UCL	12.23	12.23	12.23	12.23	12.23	12.23	12.23	12.23
	LCL	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.52
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	8.37	8.37	8.37	8.37	8.37	8.37	8.37	8.37
	UCL	13.59	13.59	13.59	13.59	13.59	13.59	13.59	13.59
	LCL	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14	3.14

Figure 1. Graphical forecasting analysis for I19

References

Covaci, B./Suciu, M. C./Covaci, M. (2018): Sectoarele secundar și terțiar, suport al dezvoltării montane în regiunea de Nord-Est a României, in: *Journal of Montanology*, 9, IX, 129-137.

Covaci, M. (2017): Spearman correlations between learning styles from rational level and Gardner intelligence types, in: *Romanian Journal of Psychological Studies*. Hyperion University, 5, 2, 31-38.

Covaci, M. (2019): The Vark Model Investigated at the students from PPPE, in: *Journal of Education Studies (JES)*. Adventus University, 1, 1, 12-19

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a. The Viability Of The Mountainous Region In Northeastern Romania Is Supported By The Sectors Of Wholesale And Retail Trade, As Well As The Repair Of Motor Vehicles And Motorcycles. *Mountain Perspective Journal* 1/2021

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021b. Organizational Dynamics In Mountainous Regions: Navigating Challenges And Fostering Sustainable Development. *Mountain Perspective Journal* 1/2021

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021c. Theoretical Framework For Examining Entrepreneurship In Mountainous Regions. *Mountain Perspective Journal* 1/2021

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021d. The Current Landscape Of Mountain Entrepreneurship In Europe: An In-Depth Analysis. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2021

46

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021e. Entrepreneurship In The Romanian Mountains: Exploring Probiotic Properties In Vegetable Products. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2021

46

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021f. Predictive Analysis Of Food And Service-Centric Entrepreneurship In Mountainous Regions: Insights From Agritourism. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2021

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021g. Food And Services Sectors In Central And Eastern European Countries. Case Study Of Mountain Area. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2021

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021h. Romanian Mountain Entrepreneurs Of Dairy And Beekeeping Products: A Biotic Perspective. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2021

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022a. Investigating Science, Technology, And Research Infrastructure In The European Mountainous Region: A Comprehensive Analysis From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022b. Hospitality And Culinary Service Operations In European Mountainous Regions From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022

47

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022c. Economic Analysis Of Financial, Insurance, And Real Estate Activities In European Mountainous Regions From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022

47

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022d. Exploring Financial And Insurance Activities, Real Estate Operations In The Romanian Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 1/2022

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022e. Evolution Of The Construction Sector In Romanian Mountain Macroregions From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022f. Exploring Sector-Specific Progress In Wholesale And Retail Trade, Motor Vehicle, And Motorcycle Repair In The Romanian Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022g. Investigating Sector-Specific Advancements In Transportation And Storage In The Romanian Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2022h. Exploring Sector-Specific Advancements In Accommodation And Food Service Activities Within The Romanian Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Mountainous Region From 2008 To 2018: An Academic Inquiry. Mountain Perspective Journal 2/2022

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2023a. An In-Depth Analysis Of Business Growth In The Romanian Mountainous Region: A 2008-2018 Perspective.

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2023b. Enterprise Dissolution Trends In A Romanian Mountain Area: An Analysis Of Dissolution Rates During The Reference Period 2008-2018. Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2023c. Unveiling Statistical Insights: Analysis Of Descriptive Measures And Forecast Models For Newly Formed Enterprises In A Romanian Mountainous Area. A Case Study Spanning 2008-2018.

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Covaci B & Covaci M, 2023d. Employment Patterns In Closed Enterprises: Total Workforce In The Romanian Mountain Area From 2008 To 2018.

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021a. Considerations Regarding The Influence Of Entropy In Organizations. A Mountain View. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021b. Online Learning In The Pandemic Era: A Statistical Analysis Of Course Trends. A Mountain Approach. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021c. Navigating Entropy: The Influence Of Organizational Culture. A Mountain Perspective. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

49

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021d. Deciphering Organizations And Entropy - A Mountain Context. Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2021)

49

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021e. World Contexts Of Entrepreneurship, As Support For Specific Economic Contexts Of Mountain Investments. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021f. Entrepreneurial Endeavors In The Romanian Mountains: Industry, Construction, And Services. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021g. Professional, Scientific And Technical, Administrative And Support Of The Romanian Mountain Activities. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2021h. Education, Human Health And Social Assistance Activities Of The Romanian Mountain Activities. Psycho-Social View Journal (2/2021)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022a. Statistical Overview Of Information And Communication Sector Advancements In The Romanian Mountain Region (2008-2018). Psycho-Social View Journal (1/2022)

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022b. An In-Depth Statistical Analysis Of Financial And Insurance Activities, Real Estate Developments In The Romanian Mountain Area: A Decadal Perspective (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (1/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022c. A Decade In Review: Evolution Of Education, Human Health, And Social Assistance Sectors In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (1/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022d. Ten Years Of Cultural Flourish: Developments In The Arts, Entertainment, Recreation Sectors, And Other Service Activities In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (1/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022e. Entrepreneurial Resilience In The Romanian Mountain Region: A Decade Of Growth And Challenges For Active Enterprises (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (2/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022f. A Tale Of Resilience: An Analysis Of Dissolved And Newly Established Enterprises In The Romanian Mountain Sector Surviving Until 2018. *Psycho-Social View Journal* (2/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022g. Navigating Economic Peaks: A Comprehensive Analysis Of Employment Trends In The Population Of Active Enterprises In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (2/2022)

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2022h. Employment Horizons: An In-Depth Examination Of Employability In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (2/2022)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2023a. Statistics Trends Regarding Persons Employed In The Last Three Years (2018), In The Romanian Mountain Area. *Psycho-Social View Journal* (1/2023)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2023b. The Employment Landscape In Newly Established Enterprises: A Decadal Analysis In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (1/2023)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2023c. Unveiling Economic Vitality: Exploring The Average Size Of Newly Established Enterprises In The Romanian Mountain Area (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (1/2023)

Covaci M & Covaci B. 2023d. Pioneering Economic Growth: Examining The Rate Of Newly Established Enterprises With Paid Employees In The Romanian Mountains (2008-2018). *Psycho-Social View Journal* (1/2023)

Covaci-Sterpu. Rapoarte de cercetare doctorală. Universitatea din Oradea. European Commission (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32012R1151> (Accessed: 14 June 2021)

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

European Commission, (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term mountain product. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0665> (Accessed: 14 June 2021)

Eurostat, (2020). Business Demography Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/fpmXZA> (Accessed: 12 January 2020)

Eurostat, (2020). Regional GDP. Available at <https://goo.gl/EoyR38>. (Accessed: 14 February 2020)

Eurostat (2020). Structural Business Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/KMtkVV>. (Accessed: 2 March 2020)